
Article

Deceptive Reciprocity

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In modernity, what is becoming increasingly clear is the symbiotic relationship between human sociality and communication technology and with this comes a development in practices which are governed by the unspoken rules and norms around its usage. Deception is embedded in the normative values and practices which are deemed as such, with social media allowing for the orchestration of a desired and highly filtered narrative to a specified audience. The following is an autoethnographic account in observations of anomic and trickster like states which are induced by both the architecture of its very design and the normalisation of deceptive strategies to paradoxically present the idealised self-while simultaneously aid in self-preservation. To set the tone the following is an introduction to what will be referred to as ‘The scene’, to stand at the periphery of the scene as an onlooker involves just as much engagement as being fully invested in the scene, as to be on the periphery is to be fully invested. This in itself is rather paradoxical, but the very nature of the scene is a paradox in itself. To merely hear about the scene is to be fully invested in it, and in this regard, at times the scene can seem inescapable.

It is completely deluded to even consider being at the periphery of the scene, as an eager and keen observer because ultimately at times you can’t anticipate playing an active role within it. The most common difficulty encountered by the anthropologist in an ethnographic study, is the issue of distance and the equilibrium between both engagement via participant observation and clearly defining a boundary between the studied social environment and the researcher’s own objectivity. Due to this precise reason, it was far more beneficial to conduct an autoethnographic style approach, providing a more nuanced and focused account of subjective personal experience and relaying this with wider social processes and theoretical engagement to help with interpretation.

The methods congruent with this study are heavily based upon participant observation using a qualitative mode of data collection with the compilation of field notes which documented observations, conversations with peers and any additional insights or thoughts. The decision for application of autoethnographic apparatus was also prompted by the type of responsibility one has to their informants as the type of issues dealt with are contentious and informants wished to remain anonymous throughout the course of this study. During the duration of research, it has forced a complete revision in the conceptual awareness of anomie and initially the definition which would have resonated with the research was more focused on “anomic structures” and cyberspace as creating a social environment which induces a state of normlessness. Taking the Durkheimian stance, the architecture of particular social media sites are either more or less anomic inducing than others, not necessarily producing an environment of normlessness because these norms exist but increasing the likelihood of producing momentary states of anomie and subsequent effects.

The scene as it is ascribed in the onset is set during the liminal state induced by ‘the college experience’, furthermore it is important to understand what the college experience is at essence? It’s best to define the socio-cultural environment at face value and categorically speaking the college experience may be

described as a rite of passage in contemporary society, with the progression of students into their professional lives. “The notion that an individual’s life consists of a series of transitions, structured by the society one lives in, and that these consist of three stages- separation by the old role, a liminal period between roles, and then the assumption of the new role.” (Arnold Van Gennep, David. I Kertzer, 2019). The college experience may be viewed in the light of a positive experience as in contemporary society we lack certain rites of passage and the ritualisation of the lived experience as in traditional society, however prolonged liminal states produce some negative consequences. It is justifiable to state that the quote ‘college experience’ is not quite what one would imagine and is so often marketed as ‘the best years of your life’. Something which people fail to mention is that it can be quite a challenging time for some. The basis of the college experience is about the seeking out of novel experiences and oftentimes this results in the transgression of certain prohibition, the college experience is characterised by the expression of certain risk-taking behaviours which are exhibited in correlation to the consequences of a prolonged liminal state. An important aspect about rites of passage is the idea of sacrifice to successfully transgress the liminal period in between roles in the successful assumption of the new role, with sacrifice used to attain a new status or role within society. The college experience does not require us to make bodily sacrifice as in traditional society, however, there is a great deal of sacrifice, in the sense that college students in most instances must leave the familial unit and oftentimes involve in the parting ways of creature comforts with having to live in squalor in student accommodation, and part ways with financial stability. The college experience as a rite of passage isn’t all that different from traditional rites of passage in the sense of ‘sacrifice’ and having to give up something to successfully achieve a new status within society.

There is no denying that my own experience of college has invertedly shaped my perspective. My academic journey has been far from plain sailing, and I have faced a number of difficulties throughout the last three years, this is by no means an isolated occurrence as many college students face similar problems. However, I do find importance in giving accurate context which has shaped this subjective account. I completed my second level education under strange circumstances, and my entrance into third level was met with remote delivery of lectures, due to the covid-19 pandemic, safe to say I didn’t have the typical experience of college so therefore I have always felt a certain distance with the quote ‘college experience’ and at times I felt as though I was located on the margins.

There have also been times where I have lost sense of direction as I was faced with a multiplicity of different options, and in this loss of direction I’ve had moments where I had to self-evaluate and ask the question ‘what am I doing with my life? This is where I give thanks to the discipline of anthropology, which has forced me to reconcile with where I fit in the scheme of things relative to the social environment in which I subsist, the discipline of anthropology has insighted in me a hyper-vigilance of social playing fields and ultimately this hyper vigilance has spurred the eureka moment which commenced the writing of this dissertation. Being equipped with the type of skills accrued by anthropological enquiry has proven advantageous giving my autoethnographic report substance with recollection of my own subjective experience coupled with the type of hyper vigilance to constantly consider the wider social implications and taking a step back to critically evaluate social phenomenon. From submersion into the scene, it became abundantly clear that snapchat was the preferred choice of social media with the user interface offering a more tailored, personal and temporary experience. The following autoethnographic account is solely based on the use of snapchat among college students because it offers the most comprehensive overview of the augmented reality we subsist to date, alternatively as previously stated the symbiosis of communication technology and human sociality. The chief observance(s) I have witnessed whilst in the scene are principally the type of strategies in deception used for self-expression, self-preservation and building human relationships.

There is stark contrast between what is posted to snapchat and other social media outlets, drunken nights out with friends, swimming in fountains and downing shots at a bar is typical to the type of content which is openly shared among friends via snapchat and this is because of snapchats temporariness with anything posted disappearing after a 24-hour period. I have come to surmise that there

are particular strategies of deception which serve a dualized function in, (a) The idealised presentation of self and (b) The preservation of self-image, this level of systemised deception is not even recognised as such. The very architecture of snapchats design allows for more anomic inducing effects, snapchat offers users the option to create private stories allowing for the sharing of daily life occurrences with a select few and aids in the upkeep of a specific image tailored to a specified audience. What was not anticipated was the use of the private story function in the weaving of often exaggerated scenarios in the presentation of the idealised self-image. Whilst presenting the idealised self or peculiar narrative is at the forefront of the private story, it also acts as a means of self-preservation, serving a dualized function of sorts providing a platform for open expression with the mitigation of risk associated with soliciting disapproval from some. What is highly suggestive of this is the stark contrast between the type of content posted to private stories and the more public forms of media. The trickster has never had a stable archetypical representation and is characterised as having the ability to shapeshift into something entirely different and in this sense it does beg the question, do we all embody trickster logic when we use social media with the digital age allowing people to present how they want to be perceived, and does the architecture of certain types of social media mediate more trickster and anomic like states?

The following is a descriptive analysis and demonstration of the inter-play between the use of social media and its governance by normative values which dictate how it may be used and how connection may be established. What occurs first is a reciprocal act which seemingly initiates closeness; however, this is far from the case, deception begins under the guise of reciprocity with the very establishment of connection. My gift to you is your increased view on my life's daily intimacies, and your gift to me is virtually the same? It is a fool's game and essentially ends up in a stalemate with the same type of ploy used by both parties. This does not always play out exactly in this manner as there is opportunity for both negative and positive reciprocal exchange but for those with a greater footing within the scene are very much aware yet still engage with this ploy. It begs the question; how does a reciprocal exchange serve any sort of function if the initiation of quote 'closeness' is not quite as close which one would anticipate? The paradox here is that reciprocity is the supposed basis for human connection and cohesion so what is the function of this intangible and free gift within the scene? What I would soon discover is the idea that obligation dictates exchange and until the establishment of furthered trust, then and only then are you deemed worthy enough for the less filtered social narrative. Proximity effects reciprocity, "given proximity effects, roommates may like each other more than non-roommates. This effect of proximity will create reciprocity."(Kenny, David A, Lawrence La Voie 1982) As characterised in contemporary work there is a common trend within the literature that suggests the type of perceived proximity will mediate the type of exchange and the regularity of its occurrence, and hence the free gift represents a socially binding contract, inter-changeable, deceptive and dependent upon perceived 'closeness' by both parties.

They say dreams have a greater depth of meaning, initially cryptic and seemingly nonsensical, yet given further consideration can provide insight into the human subconscious mind. The reiteration of experience for my autoethnographic account was coupled with an exploration into the theoretical basis of the trickster and anomie, what is bazar is how the trickster intercepted my dreams and left me with a few sleepless nights, transforming something which on the onset seemed so abstract and inaccessible into something which was tangible and capable to manifest in my very own subconscious mind. The dream began with being in some strange, unrecognisable place surrounded by precisely 13 individuals, ironically by some strange coincidence the number of people in my graduating year is also 13... the trickster manifested itself as a demon who consumes human flesh, and gives us all an ultimatum, each day he will return in request of a human bodily sacrifice, or we all face imminent death. Each day, piece by piece, bit by bit, I and the 13 other individuals make sacrifice, until eventually we are left as a torso, no legs to run, no eyes to see, no fists to fight, essentially the trickster renders us unable to escape due to our own naivety, with encouragement of self-butchery. Is this essentially metaphorical for the type of competition driven academic experience in the final year of our degree? Has the trickster logic consumed us in our drive to be better than the other? Are we all embodying trickster discourse in reason? Due to placing a premium on subjectivity, it would be hypocritical to not leave this down to the readers own subjective

interpretation, but what is made abundantly clear is that the human experience of cyber space is one governed by the interplay between human desire and deception.

Reciprocity

With the onset of the study, reciprocity was explored through the Maussian sense of exchange through the first English translation of his work 'the gift' in (1954), this was also explored in Elizabeth Whitakers 'A Macat Analysis Marcell Mauss's *The Gift*' (2017). The traditional sense of the gift has since seen revisions to fit within a modern context and is seen in Marion Fourcade and Daniel N Kluttz work, 'A Maussian bargain: Accumulation by gift in the digital economy' (2020). Similarly, the gift in modernity is expressed in the work 'Reciprocity as a key concept for social media and society' (2015). A common trend within contemporary revisions of the gift is the idea that 'data' has become the gift within modernity while this provides interesting perspective, the gap which persists in contemporary literature is a lack of exploration into the exchange of social media and the building of interpersonal connections from this very initiation of exchange. The gap in literature is addressed in the second section of the dissertation, 'deceptive reciprocity' the gift is explored through the exchange of social media, the building of interpersonal connection and the exchanges paradoxical function in this type of exchange.

Anthropology has most often been concerned with studying the other to better the understanding of ourselves, while this in part can be highly insightful it has also produced a major oversight in practice, and forces one to consider, 'how can we even begin to study the other if we fail to study ourselves?' One of the main research objectives is to make advancement with brining anthropological enquiry up to speed as there is a great niche to be filled for the more holistic approaches and specific skill sets rendered by anthropological thought.

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